

USE OF CYTOFLAVIN FOR THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM THE PRIMARY OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA**Tuychibaeva D.M.,***Doctor of Dental Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Ophthalmology,
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Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 100047, Yashnabad district, Makhtumkuli street 103***Abstract**

The term "glaucoma" unites a large group of eye diseases of various origins with a progradient, chronic course.

The aim of this study was to study the neuroprotective effect of Cytoflavin in patients with POAG with normalized IOP based on the clinical and functional parameters of the organ of vision.

Material and methods. The study involved 60 patients diagnosed with primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) stage I, II and III. All patients were divided into 2 groups depending on the treatment received.

Results. Cytoflavin has a pronounced neuroprotective effect in POAG, effectively protecting the nervous tissue and slowing down apoptosis. In addition to improving the clinical and functional indicators of the organ of vision, we noted an improvement in overall well-being, attention and overall performance in all patients.

Conclusions. Analysis of the obtained results indicates a rather high clinical efficacy of Cytoflavin in the conservative treatment of patients with POAG with compensated IOP and can be recommended as a background neuroprotective therapy.

Keywords: primary open-angle glaucoma, neuroprotective treatment, Cytoflavin, visual functions, glaucoma process.

Actuality. Glaucoma has become one of the leading medical and social problems of modern healthcare, growing in importance from year to year. According to literary sources, glaucoma is one of the most common diseases of the organ of vision and has a high medical and social significance, often leads to blindness and low vision, and is the leading cause of disability due to ophthalmic pathology.

The term glaucoma refers to a large group of eye-diseases of various genesis with progradiental chronic course. As a rule, glaucoma is concomitant to increase of the intraocular pressure (IOP), except for glaucoma with low (so-called – pseudo glaucoma) pressure, developed optic neuropathia having characteristic altered manifestations in the retinal fibres of the optic nerve capitulum and progressive worsening of the visual functions resulting in the development of typical defects of the visual field [1,3].

The primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) is the chronic disease effecting mostly the working-age population and the elder groups. Among all types of glaucoma cases this type of the disease is more numerous and constitutes 80% of the total number of the cases [2]. Every year one person of every 1000 ones of the 40-45 years old groups falls ill. Nowadays about 60-70 millions of patients of the world suffer from glaucoma and every ten one of them have already become blind. In Uzbekistan in 2021 the incidence rate of POAG was 1.6% [16,18]. For the period from 2012 to 2021 in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of people recognized as disabled for the first time due to glaucoma increased by 2.5 times, the number of people with general disability increased by 1.3 times [15,17,19].

Depending on the stage of the glaucomatosis a part of nerve fibres of the optic nerve undergoes atrophy and the other part of them is at the parabiosis state. It allows to hope that restoration of their functions is possible by the therapeutic or surgical methods of treatment [5,6].

Nowadays the therapeutic treatment of glaucoma is carried out in three main directions:

- the therapy aimed to decrease the intraocular blood pressure (IOP);
- the therapy providing improvement of blood supply in the internal ocular layers and the intraocular part of the optic nerve;
- the therapy aimed to normalize metabolism in the eye tissue by effecting the dystrophic processes being typical for glaucoma (neuroprotective therapy) [4,8].

As it was truly marked by T.Yamamoto in 2001, the neuroprotective therapy of glaucoma would become the basic therapy used for the treatment of this serious disease in the nearest future.

The essence of the neuroprotective treatment is to prevent the cascade of reactions defecting the neurons, mainly being the result of the ischemia development. It should be pointed out that it concerns namely, the consequently developed reactions in which new and new neurons are involved in the pathologic process unless the defected tissue surrounding them becomes the source of the pathologic processes. That is why the neuroprotective treatment should be carried out within the limits of the so-called therapeutic frame (window) before the effected nerve tissue has not become irreversible [9].

In a number of papers published by foreign scientists the efficiency of "Cytoflavin" (POLYSAN NTFF LLC (Russia)) used for the restoration of the optic functions in patients suffering from the primary open-angle glaucoma have been described [9,12,14]. Cytoflavin enhances the intensity of aerobic glycolysis, which leads to the activation of glucose utilization and β -oxidation of fatty acids, and also stimulates the synthesis of γ -aminobutyric acid in neurons. It also increases the resistance of the membranes of nerve and glial cells to ischemia, which is expressed in a decrease in the concentration of neurospecific proteins that characterize the level of destruction of the main structural components of the nervous tissue, improves coronary and cerebral blood flow, activates metabolic processes in the central nervous system, preventing cell death, affects the mechanisms of apoptosis and improves the transmission of nerve impulses in cholinergic neurons [10,11,13].

Considering the pathogenetic basis the aim of our research work was to study the neuroprotective influence of Cytoflavin drug on the patients with POAG having normalized IOP basing on the clinic and functional data of the visual organ.

Material and methods. Sixty patients (38 women and 22 men), their average age was $60,75 \pm 12,83$ with the diagnosed open-angle glaucoma at I, II, III stages. The disease duration was from 6 months to 10 years, in average $3,1 \pm 0,6$ years. The examined patients included in this group were the patients whose IOP was achieved either by drug therapy or surgery and did not undergo neuroprotective treatment during the last six-months period.

All the patients were divided in two groups – basic and control ones. Both groups of patients were representative by their basic clinical indications. The control

group included 28 patients (47 eyes) who were given the routine traditional therapy: 1% solution of Emoxypine in 1,0 ml dose parabulbarly; 10% solution of Pyracetam 5,0 ml dose intravenously; 1% solution of Riboflavine mononucleotide in 1,0 ml dose, 5% solution of Pyridoxine hydrochloride in 1,0 ml dose, 5% solution of Ascorbic acid in 2,0 ml dose intramuscular injection for 10 days; One pill of Cavinton 3 times a day, Aevit one pill three times a day during one months.

The basic group included 32 patients (52 eyes) and were treated by the traditional therapy and Cytoflavin (Cytoflavin® POLYSAN NTFF LLC Russia), which was administered intravenously in isotonic solution for 10 days, at a dose of 10 mg/day.

All the patients were examined by: visometria with the optimal correction, biomicroscopia, computer perimetria on the Humphrey field analyser (HFA II 740), gonioscopia, tonographia, eye- bottom examination with Volk lens, optic cocherred tomography (OCT), defined the threshold of the optic nerve electric sensitivity and lability by phosphene, controlled the patient's adherence to the treatment.

There were specified side effects, keeping to the instillation regime, change in the patientis self-appraisal of his (her) mood and state.

The clinical efficiency of the treatment has been estimated by: visual acuity (V.A), mean deviation of the retinal photosensitivity in the central zone, threshold of the phosphene electric sensitivity (ThPhES) critical frequency of phosphene fusion flickers (CFPh F.F) at the "3,0" regime.

Results and Discussion

Good local and systemic durability to Cytoflavin was observed at every stage in the course of treatment.

Fig.1. The visual acuity dynamics before and after the treatment

Note: p – reliability of various indices if compared to that before the treatment at the same stage of POAG

It is demonstrated on fig.1 that V.A of patients of the basic group has reliably improved after the therapy and was $0,80 \pm 0,02$ at the first stage of the disease; $0,54 \pm 0,02$ at the second stage and $0,23$ at the third stage. The V.A of patients in the control group was: $0,79 \pm ,02$ at the first stage; $0,38 \pm 0,02$ at the second stage and

$0,10 \pm 0,02$ at the third stage. There was noted some improvement of the eye-vision in this group but the indices are not reliable ($p > 0,05$).

Thus, treatment of the patients with POAG by the drugs according to the scheme elaborated by us, the V.A has reliably improved to $0,08 \pm 0,2$, that is four

times higher than that after the traditional therapy. This is, by our opinion, the result of correct selection of the drugs combinations, taking into consideration the continuity of the therapeutic effect and their synergism. It is known that V.A at POAG is not the objective indicator for GON but nevertheless it influences essentially on the patient's life quality.

The functions of the inner layers of the retina and the axial band of the optic nerve have been estimated by the method used for definition the ThPhES and electric lability by phosphene (CFPhFF) in the examined patients suffering from POAG.

Fig.2. Change in the Threshold of electric sensitivity by Phosphene

Note: p – reliability of various indices if compared to that before its treatment at the same stage of POAG.

It is demonstrated in the fig.2, that in the basic group of patients with the first stage of POAG the threshold of electric sensitivity to phosphene was $138,8 \pm 9,3 \mu\text{kA}$ before the therapy, after the treatment the index became reliably lower ($p < 0,001$) (by 22,7%) and was $107,3 \pm 6,4 \mu\text{kA}$ if compared to that of prior the treatment at the same stage of the disease designated as 100%; at the second stage of POAG the index was $170,8 \pm 13,0 \mu\text{kA}$ before the therapy and after the therapy it has reliably ($p < 0,001$) decreased (by 20,7%) to $135,4 \pm 10,9 \mu\text{kA}$ if compared to the indices before the treatment at the same stage of the disease designated as 100%. At the third stage of POAG the index before the therapy was $210,7 \pm 17,2 \mu\text{kA}$ and after the treatment it has become reliably lower ($p < 0,001$) (by 17%) to $175,6 \pm 12,8 \mu\text{kA}$ if compared to that of prior the treatment at the same stage of the disease designated as 100%.

In the control group at the first stage of POAG the ThPhES index was $130,0 \pm 7,0 \mu\text{kA}$ before the treatment and after the treatment it has reliably ($p < 0,001$) decreased (by 7,6%) if compared to the indices before the treatment indicated as 100% and was $120,1 \pm 6,5$

μkA ; at the second stage of POAG before the therapy index was $177,4 \pm 11,3 \mu\text{kA}$ and after the treatment it has become insignificantly lower ($p < 0,05$) to $157,9 \pm 11,6 \mu\text{kA}$, by 10,9% lower if compared to that designated as 100%; at the third stage of POAG the index was $208,7 \pm 16,5 \mu\text{kA}$ before the treatment and after that it has become significantly lower ($p < 0,05$) to $198,5 \pm 16,8 \mu\text{kA}$, by 4,9% less if compared to the indices before the treatment at the same stage of the disease.

It was revealed that if the first drug recommended to the patient were droplets of the Prostaglandine analogues group the ThPhES index was usually less than that in the other groups. This is obviously the result of achievement the target pressure more quickly and retaining the electric sensitivity of nerve fibres and also the neuroprotective effect of the drug itself. The ThPhES higher efficiency we have noted also in patients of the basic group with less period of the POAG disease duration who was given the combined therapy during course of complex treatment. The results of investigation of the C Ph FFF indices of the examined patients with POAG are presented in fig.3.

Fig.3. Changes in the CPhFFF in patients with POAG

Note: p – reliability of the index differences when compared to that before the treatment at the same stage of POAG

Fig.3 demonstrates the reliable growth of the CPhFFF indices by 14,5% in average (before the treatment – $33,8 \pm 1,5$; after the treatment – $38,70 \pm 0,87$) at the first stage and by 13,9% at the second stage (before the treatment – $27,30 \pm 0,76$; after the treatment – $31,1 \pm 0,5$) while in the control group it was by 2,7 and 2,4% respectively if compared to the indices before the treatment at the same stage of the disease, indicated as 100%. It is reliably lower than in the patients of the first group, treated by the recommended by us therapy. This

indicates the reliably higher activation of the retinal ganglions cell and their axons in the patients of the basic group.

Thus, use of the Cytoflavin in the complex therapy for the patients with POAG helps to activate to a greater degree the visual analyzer.

The results of investigation of the threshold sensitivity of the retina (dB) according to the data obtained by the computer statistic Humphrey perimetria are given in fig.4.

Fig.4. Change of the retinal threshold sensitivity obtained by the computer statistic Humphrey perimetria

Note: p – reliability of the index's distinction in comparison with its value prior the therapy at the same stage in POAG.

Fig.4 demonstrates that in patients with POAG at the first stage the threshold of retinal sensitivity was $4,50 \pm 0,08$ dB before the treatment, after the treatment the index increased reliably ($p < 0,001$) by 22,2% and was $3,50 \pm 0,07$ dB; at the stage II the POAG index before the treatment was $7,20 \pm 0,08$ dB, after the therapy the index increased ($p < 0,001$) by 15.3% and was to $6,10 \pm 0,09$ dB if compared to that before the treatment at the same stage of the disease indicated as 100%; at the third stage the POAG index prior the therapy was $11,7 \pm 0,09$ dB and after the treatment increased ($p < 0,001$) (by 9,4%) to $10,6 \pm 0,08$ dB if compared to the index before the treatment at the same stage of the disease.

In the second group (fig.4) at the first stage of POAG the threshold of the retinal sensitivity was $4,6 \pm 0,1$ dB before the treatment and after the treatment the

index ($p < 0,05$) increased (by 4,3%) and was $4,40 \pm 0,09$ dB; at the second stage of POAG the index before the treatment was $7,00 \pm 0,13$ dB and after the therapy it increased ($p > 0,05$) to $6,8 \pm 1,4$ dB being by 2,9% higher if compared to the index before the treatment at the same stage of the disease taken for 100%; at the third stage of POAG the index before the therapy was $11,5 \pm 0,13$ dB, and after the treatment it elevated ($p > 0,05$) to $11,3 \pm 0,08$ dB which was by 1,7% higher if compared to the data before the treatment at the same stage.

According to the data obtained by computer statistic Humphrey perimetria, there was increase in the photosensitivity of retina, decrease in quantity, size and depth of the scotoma, widening the area with normal photosensitivity in patients of the basic group (fig.5).

Fig.5.

Humphrey perimetry of the left eye of the patients with second stage of POAG before and after the treatment.

Thus, Cytoflavin induces marked neuroprotective effect at POAG, rendering the effective protection of the nerve tissue and slow down the apoptosis. Besides the improvement of the clinic and functional indices of the visual organ we have observed the improvement of the general feeling, attention and working ability in all the patients.

Conclusion:

1. Analysis of the obtained results indicated to high enough clinic efficiency of Cytoflavin drug for the conservative treatment of patients with POAG and compensated IOP.
2. This drug might be recommended as the background neuroprotective therapy.

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